

ISic3723

I.Sicily inscription 3723

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic (pietra di Fuardo)

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory 12275

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Τιμασώ

Apparatus

Meligunìs Lipára XII

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

PHI 334167

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 34.0958.5

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 65

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 83 no.12
Moretti, L. 1984. Epigraphica. 27. Liparitana. *Rivista di Filologia e di Istruzione
Classica*. 112: 318-324. At 319

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-21): ISic3723. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI
edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4381458>